

Topic: Labor Relations

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Impacts of contemporary trade

Trade has been growing remarkably over the last two centuries, changing the face of the global economy with it. This tremendous growth of trade is also transforming trade itself and making it a global economic activity enabling exportation and importation of goods (Jafari & Britz, 2017). It is undergoing a transformative process in the face of technological advancements has generated a gamut of gains and important distributional consequences. The emergence of e-commerce and modern retail has greatly impacted the global economy and lives. This paper aims to look into the impacts of contemporary trade.

E-commerce trade has been hailed to reduce the overall carbon imprint globally by 30% as compared to the traditional retail setting that requires a display and security lighting, temperature regulation, operation fixtures such as registers and fixture installations. This constitutes an in-store carbon imprint that adds to the energy and carbon emission during employee and consumer transportation to and from work or store commuting. Another portion of carbon emission and energy wasting comes from the building and renovating structures necessary for housing and business operation.

The life span of many products such as clothing, bags, and books have been extended with the help of such websites as eBay, ThredUP, and Etsy as they cut back on the amount of new product purchases and in such cutting back on fast fashion. This is a significant contribution

to the global carbon and global warming issues. Entrepreneurial independence has also been gained from the use of such websites as amazon.com that allow delivery of products to the homes of consumers and in this process enhancing convenience and entrepreneurial independence (Sabel, 2019).

Contemporary trade, through modern retail, is facilitating global economic growth as it positively impacts such constituencies as the government, consumers, organized trade participants, and producers/farmers. Transitional economies such as China and India, attribute a big chunk of their economic growth rates to modern trade as such components of modern retails as chain stores, supermarkets, mall shopping, and departmental stores are quickly replacing the unorganized sector in these countries, attracting global investors and consumers. In such, contemporary trade reduces wastage across the supply chain, strengthens the position of host nations as world sourcing hubs, introduces increased choice and variety of products into the market, levels the playing field in terms of lifestyle parity and ushers in vital technology and technological investment and transfer of best practices.

The growth of these contemporary retail stores, apart from the aforementioned benefits, come with others such as a wide range of product choices, rationalization and convergence of process, better food and non-food product quality, equalization of living standards between countries and zero tolerance policy for inefficiencies such as substandard goods and inefficient services (Dhingra & Freeman, 2018).

Modern trade also benefits the exchequer as it contributes to the flow into national tax baskets due to increased transparency in tax collection in the face of increased employment of technology in trade. The contemporary trade also integrates the unorganized sector and increases

employment opportunities as well as engaging small vendors through partnership models in the ever-changing business environment. Studies show an expected increase in individual needed for retail operations globally to fill in staff positions in malls, departmental stores, supermarkets, hypermarkets, and convenience stores in the coming years as their prominence grows and in the process generating both direct and indirect employment opportunities.

Globalization has played an important role in changing the world economy as it has given rise to multinational companies exploring customers from all over the world. Globalization as one of the elements of modern trade has had huge impacts on trade, economy and lives all over the world. National economies have been integrated into global economic systems and have resulted in remarkable growth in trade between countries.

Contemporary trade helped grow the Gross Domestic Product (GDP) of countries all over the world as sustained economic growth has been experienced in the world economy. This has made trade a fundamental part of the economic activity globally with countries exchanging both final and intermediate inputs creating an intricate network of economic interactions covering the whole world. Modern trade has also been hailed for generating efficiency gains as global economic integration brings with it growth enhancing factors such as completion, economies of scale, and learning and innovation. It has also distributional consequences since it interlinks markets. This means that both imports and exports affect commodity prices in the economy affecting distribution.

Unionism on business decision making

Worker participation schemes should be seen in relation to the industrial relations within which they operate. Managers and trade unions have in the past have either been apathetic or

resisted participative schemes and have instead opted to conduct their relations and businesses through mechanisms for compulsory arbitration (Heckscher, 2018). The participation of workers in decision making at the organization level, rather than at the national level is still low despite the increased willingness to consult and the growth in the use of negotiated agreements. These have rendered participation practices uneven and not well-developed. This has been complemented by the lack of interest among trade unions and employers in increased participation for fear that the proposed changes might limit or restrict some of their existing powers.

The need for change is brought about by the virtual disappearance of managerial prerogatives, the spread and growth of participative management and arrangements at the national and industry level, and such funds and superannuation funds which are managed by employers and unions, new legislations worldwide requiring consultative and participatory decision-making processes, the need to adjust to technological change that have resulted in tribunal orders requiring consultation, the search for improved productivity that requires bargaining at different levels and efforts aimed at transforming industrial relations and altering traditional industrial law for the achievement of fresh focus.

The need for unionism participation in business decision-making gives workers a chance to present their views to be reflected in the decisions made. This means that participative decision making needs to be strengthened and mutual trust in companies needs to be encouraged in order to improve the prediction of risks, make the work organization more flexible and to enable training of workers in the company where safety is maintained, where workers are aware of the need to be flexible, where the competence of workers is increased for the realization of measures and activities with which they could increase their employability, and where the

inclusion of workers into the operation and future of the company is encouraged and its competitiveness is increased.

Worker participation in decision making also needs to be encouraged for the purpose of informing and consultation about the state and possible employment development inside the company. When an employer predicts that the employability in the company becomes endangered, about possible future measures, especially relating to the training and development of the workers' skills with which they would correct the negative development and its consequences and improve the employability and flexibility of workers who would be affected by such negative developments.

Participative decision-making has a range of benefits to a business and the employees including the fact that it encourages mutual trust, enhances a flexible working organization, increases awareness on the needs for flexibility, advocates for trainings for the purpose of employability, strengthens of competitiveness of the company, corrects the negative development and its consequences through training and development of skills; helps improve employability and flexibility of workers, and the reciprocity of material rights and obligations (Ji, 2018). Directly or indirectly including employees in the decision-making processes helps prevent potential conflicts and serves as a tool for early resolution. Transparency and legitimacy enhanced through early conflict resolution and decision making through employee representatives also help a business avoid a lot of business drawbacks that might affect its profitability at certain time points (Heckscher, 2018).

With the ushering in of a new industrial arena of enterprise development, workers are increasingly being appreciated and recognized as real assets in businesses, calling for their

training and involvement in decision-making processes. This in the wake of the ongoing business management shift from Taylorist models to models in which workers brains are valued and used. The decline of unions apart from being viewed as a necessary step towards increased economic prosperity also calls for participative management at company levels.

Participative decision making also holds a number of disadvantages such as lack of honesty and commitment on part f the management, social pressures to conform to group domination and dilemma that need foresight such as actor involvement and formalism in place of freedom. There exists also a range of types of participative decision making such as suggestion involvement, job involvement, and high involvement, collective, democratic, autocratic and consensus participative decision making.

References

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